

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**REGIONAL FEATURES IN IMPLEMENTATION OF THE
DEMOGRAPHY NATIONAL PROJECT**¹Mira Aslangerieva Kantemirova, ²Alla Yevgenyevna Gurina, ³Zara Ramazanovna Alikova, ⁴Zaur Leonidovich Dzagoev, ⁵Lima Aslanbievna Anaeva¹Dr .Econ.Sci., Professor at the Department of Public health, health protection and socio-economic sciences, FSBEI HE “North Ossetian State Medical Academy”, 362025, Vladikavkaz, 40 Pushkinskaya str., E-mail: kantemirova.mira@mail.ru, tel. +79188263197²Cand.Med.Sci., associate professor, Pro-rector for Academic affairs and educational work, head of the Department of Biological chemistry, FSBEI HE “North-Ossetian State Medical Academy”, 362025, Vladikavkaz, 62-64 Kuibyshev str. Fl. 52, E-mail: allagurina@yandex.ru³Dr.Med.Sci., Professor, head of the Department of Public health, health protection and socio-economic sciences FSBEI HE “North-Ossetian State Medical Academy”, 362025, Vladikavkaz, 40 Pushkinskaya str., E-mail:alikota_zr@mail.ru.⁴ Cand.Econ.Sci., associate professor at the Department of Management, FSBEI HE “North-Ossetian State University”, 362025, Vladikavkaz, 46 Vatutin str., E-mail: dzl200@rambler⁵Cand.Med.Sci., associate professor at the Department of General practice, gerontology, public health and healthcare, Medical faculty, FSBEI HE “Kabardino-Balkarian State University after Kh.M. Berbekov”, 360004, Nalchik, Russia.**Abstract:**

The implementation issues of the Demography national project in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania are considered. The forecast options were compared based on: statistical data and extrapolation of the current trend for the period 2000-2018; strategy of socio-economic development in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania up to 2030; calculation of the Russian estimated population size up to 2035 by the Federal state statistics service. The tendency of further reduction in the population size is revealed, the conclusion about necessity of improving demographic policy based on all aspects of its influence on strategic prospects of social and economic development in the Republic is made.

Keywords: demography, national project, population size, forecast, North Caucasus region, Republic of North Ossetia-Alania.

Corresponding author:**Mira Aslangerieva Kantemirova,**

Dr .Econ.Sci., Professor at the Department of Public health, health protection and socio-economic sciences, FSBEI HE “North Ossetian State Medical Academy”, 362025, Vladikavkaz, 40 Pushkinskaya str.,

E-mail: kantemirova.mira@mail.ru, tel. +79188263197

QR code

*Please cite this article in press Mira Aslangerieva Kantemirova et al., **Regional features in implementation of the Demography national project** ., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(11).*

INTRODUCTION:

The key determinant that determines the potential and prospects of socio-economic development in any state are demographic processes reflecting regularities of population replacement based on their historical conditionality [1 p. 48].

The ongoing fierce debates in the public discourse of the country connect the problems of the Russian population demography with demographic policy [2 p. 94], fertility failing, [3 p. 53], high mortality rate [4 p. 1089], aging trends [5 p. 215], socio-cultural, economic and other factors [6].

The level of demographics is influenced by scientific and engineering achievements, labor-saving technologies [7 p. 50] and regional features [8 p. 57], which require regular monitoring [9 p. 85] and rationale of the relevant social policy [10; 11].

The multidimensionality of the demographic situation and its high importance necessitated the adoption of the Federal national project "Demography" (2019-2024), the aims of which are identified.

- increase in healthy life expectancy to 67 years;
- reduction in mortality rate of the population older than working age;
- increase in the total fertility rate (up to 1,7 children per woman);
- increase in the share of citizens that keep a healthy lifestyle;
- increase in appealability to medical organizations on healthy lifestyle issues;
- increase in the number of people with individual health plans (health passports), in health centers;
- increase in the share of citizens who systematically engage in physical education and sports [12].

The Demography national project includes 5 federal programs: "Financial support for families at

birth", "Promotion of employment among women – availability of preschool education", "Older generation", "Improving public health" and "Sport is a way of life".

The Republic of North Ossetia-Alania (RNO-Alania), in order to implement the Federal national project "Demography" realizes 5 relevant regional projects that include various activities. Thus, monthly payments of 9,5 thousand roubles were introduced for 2017 families which had their first child and 2283 families with the third subsequent child. Preschool facilities, sports and recreation centres, etc. will be built. It is expected to purchase cars to deliver citizens over 65 years from rural areas of the republic to medical organizations to undergo prophylactic medical examination.

Every year, 253 people of pre-retirement age will be retrained. For the older generation, conditions for training of specialists engaged in the field of hospitality, tourism, accounting, as well as cooks and confectioners are created. By 2024, the republic intends to increase life expectancy from 75 years to more than 80 years, to ensure natural population growth of 2600 people [13;14].

In order to determine the further dynamics of the population size in the republic for the period up to 2030, the following forecast options were compared: by the authors of the article on the basis of statistical data and extrapolation of the current trend for the period 2000-2018; strategies of socio-economic development in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania up to 2030; calculation of the Russian estimated population size up to 2035 by the Federal state statistics service.

RNO-Alania is one of the regions in Russia with a relatively small population size, which amounted to about 702 thousand people in 2018. According to statistical data, since 2000, the population in the republic has ranged from a minimum value of 701 thousand people to a maximum level – 712 thousand people with the regularity of the downward trend (figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of population size in RNO-Alania
[summarized by the authors according to: 17]

As can be seen, over the period 2010-2018 the population size of the republic decreased by 10 thousand people. The forecast basing on extrapolation of the current tendencies shows that by 2030 the population size can decrease approximately to 700 thousand people, and by 2035 – to 698 thousand people.

As a whole the share of population of RNO-Alania in the total Russian population for the period 2000-2018 was relatively stable, remaining on average at the level of 0,49%, which reflects vague similarity between volatile reasons of the demographic processes occurring within them.

By population size RNO-Alania is fifth among 7 subjects of the North Caucasus region (North Caucasus Federal District) (table 1).

Table 1: Population dynamics by subjects of the North Caucasus Federal District for 2000-2018 [summarized by the authors according to: 15]

Subject	2000	2005	2010	2015	2016	2018	2018/2000, %
North Caucasus Federal District	8702	9028	9439	9718	9776	9823	112,9
Republic of Dagestan	2486	2641	2914	3015	3042	3064	123,3
Republic of Ingushetia	446	487	415	473	481	488	109,4
Kabardino-Balkar Republic	887	894	860	862	865	865	97,5
Karachay-Cherkess Republic	441	431	477	468	466	466	105,7
Republic of North Ossetia – Alania	704	702	712	704	703	702	99,7
Chechen Republic	997	1163	1275	1394	1415	1437	144,1
Stavropol Krai	2741	2710	2786	2802	2804	2801	102,2

As can be seen, the decline in population size for 2000-2018 was recorded in the Kabardino-Balkar Republic (97,5%) and the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania (99,7%). The largest growth – 144,1% was provided by the Chechen Republic.

The share of population occupied by the subjects in the total number of the North Caucasus Federal District for 2000-2018 is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. The share of population occupied by the subjects in the total number of North Caucasus Federal District [summarized by the authors according to: 15]

The largest share in the population structure of the North Caucasus Federal District for the period 2000-2018 was recorded in Stavropol Krai (28,5%) and the Republic of Dagestan (31,2%), showing multidirectional trends. In the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania there is a steady trend of decline in the share of its population in the total number of the North Caucasus Federal District from 8,1% in 2000 to 7,1% in 2017.

According to the forecasts given in the strategy of socio-economic development of the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania [16] the average annual population size in the future will be:

- according to the inertial option (while maintaining the current trend) by 2024 will decrease to 686 thousand people, and by 2030 – to 665 thousand people, or 37 thousand people in respect to level of 2018;
- according to the basic option: by 2024 – 702 thousand people, and by 2030 – 720 thousand people (an increase by 20 thousand people);
- according to the optimistic option: by 2024 it will increase to 707 thousand people, and by 2030 – to 736 thousand people (an increase by 36 thousand people).

It is necessary to note that the population growth in the basic and optimistic forecast options by 2030 is not confirmed in the strategy by the relevant

demographic indicators (fertility, mortality, etc.), as well as the resource conditions for their ensuring.

The Federal state statistics service has calculated the estimated population size of Russia and its regions for the period 2019-2035 using three options (low, medium, high) [17]. According to the calculation, the population in RNO-Alania will have the following values:

- low option: in 2024 – 684 thousand people, in 2030 – 661,8 thousand people; in 2035 – 642 thousand people, which is lower than the real value of 2018;
- average option: in 2024 – 687,3 thousand people, in 2030 – 669,9 thousand people; in 2035 – 654,4 thousand people, which is also lower than the real value of 2018;
- high option: in 2024 – 692,6 thousand people, in 2030 – 685,4 thousand people; in 2035 – 679 thousand people, which is less than the real value of 2018.

The forecast was calculated basing on hypotheses about trends in demographic indicators (fertility, mortality and migration) and showed that in all three options the population size of RNO-Alania will continue its decline. In addition, the comparison of population size changes in the subjects of the North Caucasus region allows predicting a further decline in the share of RNO-Alania in the total population of the district (table 2).

Table 2: Population size forecast in the subjects of North Caucasus Federal District for 2019-2035
[summarized by the authors according to: 17]

Subject	2019	2020	2024	2025	2030	2035	2035/2019, %
North Caucasus Federal District	9863,1	9909,6	1066,9	10105	10277,9	10445,0	105,9
Republic of Dagestan	3083,5	3104,1	3176,6	3194,3	3276,5	3355,4	108,8
Republic of Ingushetia	493,8	499,7	522,0	527,6	554,4	580,3	117,5
Kabardino-Balkar Republic	866,0	866,8	866,5	866,1	861,0	853,3	98,5
Karachay-Cherkess Republic	465,0	464,0	458,5	456,9	447,8	437,3	94,0
Republic of North Ossetia – Alania	699,3	697,3	687,3	684,6	669,9	654,4	93,6
Chechen Republic	1458,7	1481,2	1570,2	1593,6	1715,2	1848,7	126,7
Stavropol Krai	2796,8	2796,5	2785,8	2781,9	2753,1	2715,6	97,1

As can be seen, the population size in RNO-Alania will continue to decline throughout the whole period up to 2035, amounting to only 93,6% to level of 2019.

The share of population occupied by the subjects in the total number of the North Caucasus Federal District is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. The share of population occupied by the subjects in the total number of North Caucasus Federal District [summarized by the authors according to: 17]

The largest share in the population structure of the North Caucasus Federal District after 2019 will fall on the Republic of Dagestan (2035-32,1%) with prospects for further growth. The share of Stavropol Krai in the population size of the North Caucasus Federal District will continue steady decline from 28,4% in 2019 to 26% in 2035.

The forecast shows that the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania will also continue the trend of

reducing the share of its population in the total number of the North Caucasus Federal District from 7,1% in 2019 to 6,3% in 2035.

A number of demographic indicators have a significant impact on the population decline. For example, the natural population growth rate (per 1,000 people) rose from 2 in 2000 to 4,8 in 2013, and then by 2018 declined to 2,5. According to the forecast, it may decrease to 0,6 or less by 2035,

unless measures to increase the population fertility and reduce mortality are taken.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the steady growth of the share of population in the republic older than working age, while reducing the share of working age residents.

Thus, the analysis of the demographic situation in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania allows drawing the following conclusions.

1. Forecasts show a decrease in the population size of the republic while maintaining the current trends, which will lead to a decrease in its share in population of the North Caucasus Federal District and difficulties in achieving the aims and indicators of republican projects implemented within the framework of the Federal national project "Demography".

2. During the implementation of the Federal national project "Demography" (2019-2024), the population decline in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania will not stop.

3. The current situation necessitates to improve the demographic policy, based on all aspects of its impact on the strategic prospects of socio-economic development in the republic.

REFERENCES:

1. Vishnevsky A.G. Demographic brakes of the economy / A.G. Vishnevsky, E.M. Shcherbakova // Economic questions. 2018. №6. pp. 48-70.
2. Vangorodskaya S.A. Death of old age: result of demographic policy or tool of imitation activity of authorities? // Authority. 2016. №5. pp. 94-102.
3. Makarentseva A. Demographics: the number of births has begun to fall // Russian Economic developments. 2017. №8. pp. 53-57.
4. Boitsov S.A. Factors affecting the population mortality / S.A. Boitsov, I.V. Samorodskaya // Herald of the Russian Academy of Sciences. 2016. Vol. 86. №12. pp. 1089-1097.
5. Bukher S. Modern trends of population aging in Russia. Herald of the Russian Academy of Sciences. 2016. Vol. 86. №3. pp. 215-223.
6. Ignatov A.V. Socio-cultural and economic factors of territorial variability of life expectancy in the Russian Federation / A.V. Ignatov, P.L. Popov, A.A. Cherenev // Geography and natural resources. 2019. №1. pp. 118-126.
7. Akimov A.V. Demographic explosion, population aging and labor-saving technologies: interaction in the XXI century // World economy and international relations. 2016. - Vol. 60. №5. - pp. 50-60.
8. Kazenin K. Interregional diversity of fertility in Russia in 2017 and its possible correlates / K. Kazenin, A. Raksha // Russian Economic developments. 2018. №8. pp. 57-63.
9. Zubarevich N. Russian regions in 2017: social and demographic processes (based on the results of regular monitoring of INSAF RANEPa) / N. Zubarevich, R. Khasanova, N. Mkrtchyan // Russian Economic developments. 2017. Vol. 24. №12. pp. 85-98.
10. Kalabikhina I.E. Demographic wave of births and future population fluctuations in different age groups: challenges to social policy // Economic strategies. 2015. №2. pp. 2-8.
11. Lyashok V.Yu. Raising the retirement age: demographic arguments // Russian Economic developments. 2019. Vol. 26. №3. pp. 45-47.
12. National project "Demography" Website Of Government of the Russian Federation. URL: <http://government.ru/rugovclassifir/660/event/s/>
13. North Ossetia-Alania implements the national project "Demography" URL: <https://iryston.tv/ru/v-severnoj-osetii-realizuyut-natsproekt-demografiya/>.
14. National project "Demography": regional aspect. URL: <https://opalania.ru/>
15. Regions of Russia. Socio-economic indicators. Statistical handbook. – M., ROSSTAT (sampling for 2002-2019).
16. Strategy of socio-economic development of the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania up to 2030. Law №60-RZ of 18 September, 2019.
17. Estimated population size of the Russian Federation. Federal state statistics service. URL: http://old.gks.ru/wps/wcm/connect/rosstat_mai/rosstat/ru/statistics/publications/catalog/doc/1140095525812.